

ORION | Trapezium

A Monthly Publication of the ORION Astronomical Society

Two newly poured concrete pads recently appeared at TAO.

Their dimensions are approximately 18 ft. sq. (far pad) and 20 ft. sq. (near pad). This is the view to the East.

Image captured 1:09 pm Eastern, 8 Apr 2025. We look forward to the addition of telescope domes.

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Page Three Astronomy

Andromeda

(Bayer's Uranometria, 1603)

In Greek mythology, Andromeda was the daughter of Cepheus and Cassiopeia, the King and Queen of Ethiopia. Cassiopeia, a great beauty, announced that she was fairer than both Juno, the sister of Jupiter, and the Nereides, the sea nymphs. The Nereides complained to Neptune, who sent the sea monster Cetus to ravage the Ethiopian coast, and demanded that Andromeda be sacrificed to Cetus. Fortunately, Perseus arrived in time to save Andromeda from this dire fate.

The **ORION Astronomical Society** is a science and astronomy group founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and astronomical activities in East Tennessee. We hold monthly public meetings at the Oak Ridge RSCC Campus, and are active at Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO), hosting public events, sharing knowledge of the skies, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, IT experts, artists, students, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20, and student discounts are available. There is no charge for our newsletters and publications, or for participation in most ORION activities.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

VP and Program Chair: David Fields

Social Chair: Noah Frere

Secretary: Rob Fowler

Treasurer: Bob Edwards

Editor: Ted Barnes

Astrotechnologist: Rob Scott

Videographer: Rob Fowler

Obed Site Outreach: Joshua Gray.

TRAPEZIUM is a monthly publication of the ORION Astronomical Society. The issue date is the Friday preceding the monthly ORION meeting, chosen to provide timely information regarding the planned Program.

From March 2025 we will be issuing a shorter version of the Trapezium, which will still include important information regarding the monthly ORION presentation, as well as dates and other information regarding Public Stargazes and other notable events relating to ORION and TAO.

We expect to go through several iterations of this shorter Trapezium; we have already concluded that some components, such as a separate Astrophotography section, are so important for a publication on amateur astronomy that one really cannot justify excluding them.

Messages from ORION

It's galaxy season now, but in East Tennessee we seem to be in a continuing monsoon period, so it's been hard to enjoy the galaxies. The other issue is that the telescope business has gotten strange recently. I've been seeing lots of "out of stock" and "backordered" notices appearing on astronomy equipment websites due to the trade war. However, most of us are probably pretty well off as gear goes, especially as compared to 10 to 15 years ago. My advice is to appreciate/enjoy what you have. After all, as our President might say, you don't really need 30 telescopes, one or two should be enough. However, as I write this, the trade war with China (where much of our astronomy gear is made) has just been put on hold for 90 days, so maybe things will start to slowly improve.

In May, the full Moon is on the 14th (known as the Flower Moon), the new moon is May 29 (May 25, 26 is the dark sky weekend). The Sun is in solar maximum. I checked it recently with my solar scope and could pick out a large prom plus a few sunspots. Planets – not much now, except early morning or low in the sky – they'll be back in the Fall. Meteor showers: the Eta Aquarids were May 5 and 6. I didn't photograph them and don't know of anyone else that did.

Galaxies - in Canes Venatici: M106 has interesting spiral arms and is 24 Mly away; M51 has the classic two interacting/dueling galaxies and is 31 Mly away; NGC 4449 is 13 Mly away. In Coma Berenices: NGC4565, the Needle galaxy is 39 Mly; M64, the Black Eye galaxy, is 17 Mly. In Ursa Major both M82 and M81 are about 12 Mly and can be imaged together if you have a wide enough field of view.

Observatory Way

May 2025

The photo on the left shows our new road sign for the Roane State Tamke Allan Observatory. Traveling west, the sign is on the left as you turn into Observatory Way from Caney Creek Road, just past Joiner Hollow Road.

TAO Summer Events

TAO offers Public Stargazes to the community on the 1st and 3rd Saturdays of each month, weather permitting. Our usual schedule for the summer is to open at around 8:30 pm and continue to nominally around 10:30 pm, but later if the sky and attendance encourage this. These Stargazes are supported by local astronomy clubs, especially ORION members and friends, and benefit our students and community.

Our TAO Stargazes are usually well-attended, with a full classroom of visitors for evening astronomy lectures. We've recently missed many Stargazes due to inclement weather. Our next Public Stargaze is planned for the Saturday evening of May 17.

TAO Astronomers support our Astronomy Classes, our Public Stargazes, and our Special Events. Examples of special events are eclipses, planetary transits across the sun, and Asteroid Occultations.

Many of our events are highly successful, but working around the weather challenges of East Tennessee is a continuing challenge.

The Astronomer's Weather Challenge

Weather issues significantly impact TAO activities. The first weather issue is safety: We don't use the site during high winds or electrical storms.

A more frequent challenge is attempting to avoid cloudy skies. Getting weather predictions is easy, but getting "good" predictions is difficult, especially in East Tennessee, already known for chaotic weather changes. Several planned Asteroid Occultations and Public Stargazes, and one International Friendship Stargaze have been cancelled due to inclement weather. In May, we missed opportunities for all three types of events because of 'weather'.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

Over the past 5y, more astronomers are discovering the usefulness of Astrospheric (www.astrospheric.com). I've now added Astrospheric to our TAO web site, and most people are finding the weather predictions more useful than those of our Clear Sky Chart.

Evaluating the usefulness of Astrospheric vs. Clear Sky Chart

The Clear Sky Chart (CSC) provides more detailed meteorological data than does Astrospheric, whereas Astrospheric offers astronomical tools that go beyond cloud predictions.

The challenge in making cloudiness predictions is to offer useful predictions that are long-range, and that are frequently updated. The deterioration of cloud predictions for times farther into the future is discussed on the CSC website: <https://www.cleardarksky.com/c/RoaneStObkey.html> (continued on page following).

TAO Director’s Message (cont.)

“The line labeled **Cloud Cover** forecasts total cloud cover. The colors are picked from what color the sky is likely to be, with Dark Blue representing clear. Lighter shades of blue are increasing cloudiness and white is overcast. This forecast may miss low cloud and afternoon thunderstorms. When the forecast is clear, the sky may still be hazy, if the transparency forecast is poor.

Accuracy averaged over North America for a 30 day period: when the forecast is predicting less than 12 hours into the future, mostly-clear forecasts (cloud < 25%) have been right 80% of the time. Mostly-cloudy forecasts (cloud > 75%) have been right 91% of the time. When the forecast is predicting 36 to 48 hours into the future, the mostly-clear accuracy is 76% and the mostly-cloudy accuracy is 89%. Accuracy beyond 48 hours is unknown.”

Clear Sky Chart documents very well the importance of frequently updating the forecasts.

From information on these cloud prediction websites, our situation is as follows:

- 1) We can rely on the Clear Sky Chart staff to provide updates each 12 hours.
- 2) We can rely on the Astrospheric Staff to provide prediction updates each 6 hours for their basic (free) membership.
- 3) We can rely on the Astrospheric staff to provide prediction updates each hour for “Pro” users.

Their frequent updates of cloud predictions suggest that Astrospheric may be the best choice for a cloud forecast site.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

Special Pro Astrospheric option for ORION/TAO astronomers

ORION has recently achieved Pro membership for the group and makes Pro membership of Astrospheric available to TAO astronomers. Anyone wanting to avail themselves of this opportunity can follow these instructions:

Register with Astrospheric for a free account. I use the iPhone app and usually login to www.astrospheric.com.

Next, from the **Astrospheric** home page on an iPhone, Android, or browser, do this:

- + ensure you're logged into your Astrospheric account
- + click the little sparkling **S** at the upper right of the screen to enter the Subspace section;
- + select JOIN GROUP and select Oak Ridge Isochronous Observation Network (ORION); then
- + request membership.

When your request is processed, you'll become a Pro member of Astrospheric.

How to help Tamke-Allan Observatory

Amateur astronomers are always welcome to join ORION and participate in activities at TAO. Many people visit TAO, join in our activities, share their knowledge and telescopes, and even provide refreshments for our ever appreciative visitors and staff.

The history of the Observatory shows the importance of donations.

The Observatory continues to be supported by the college. Its growth and functionality is augmented by contributions of time and energy by the local amateur astronomy community, especially the ORION Astronomical Society (<http://orioninc.org>), and by donations of funds and equipment. Notable contributions include the donation of a large-aperture telescope by Dr. Roy Morrow, in memory of his grandson; the donation of a professional-quality telescope and supporting funds by Margaret Morrow, in memory of Roy and his love for astronomy; and the donation of supporting funds by Dr. William Marshall, in memory of his wife Joanne Marshall and local astronomer Mary Watson. These have all helped make the Tamke-Allan Observatory a valuable and widely appreciated community resource.

ORION Monthly Meeting

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Meeting Venue: City Room (A-111), just inside the main entrance, Coffey/McNalley Bldg., Oak Ridge Campus, Roane State Community College.

7:00 pm Eastern, 3rd Wednesday of each month.

Our monthly meetings (except for December, a dinner) generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Invited Presentation and Discussion
- Awarding of the Mug
- Astrophotography / Special Presentations

The nominal start time is 7:00 pm Eastern, on the 3rd Wednesday of the month. The beginning of the meeting will usually include announcements of general interest.

Meetings typically continue until around 9:00 pm. Please plan to stay until the end. Hopefully we will all enjoy the astrophotography and other special topics discussed in the latter part of the meeting.

Remote Viewing: A live Zoom session will usually be open during the ORION Monthly Meeting, at the link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjlhTzg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09> or
<https://bit.ly/42apGxX>

Meeting ID: 885 2873 5960 Passcode: 716689

Title: Stellar Spectroscopy for Amateur Astronomers

Speaker: Kevin A. Wilson

Abstract:

Spectroscopy is a field that is rarely explored by amateur astronomers. Until recently, the equipment needed to analyze the spectra of stars was far out of the price range of most amateurs. Recent advances in equipment have removed this barrier, however, and opened a new field for hobbyists. This lecture will introduce people to the field of spectroscopy, explain what we can learn from it, and provide a glimpse into how one can do spectroscopy as an amateur.

Title: Stellar Spectroscopy for Amateur Astronomers

Speaker: Kevin A. Wilson

Mini Bio:

Kevin A. Wilson has been an avid astronomer since he received his first telescope at age 12. He has continue his hobby into adulthood, and was most recently the Vice President and Director of the Observatory of the Astronomical Society of Greenbelt, in Maryland. With his move to Knoxville last month, he was pleased to learn about ORION, and start his membership here. Kevin is a graduate of Carson-Newman University, where he double majored in religion and political science. He went on to earn a Master's of Divinity and a Master's of Sacred Theology from Yale Divinity School. He then earned a PhD in Hebrew Bible / Old Testament and Northwest Semitic Philology From the Johns Hopkins University. He has taught college in Klaipėda, Lithuania, North Andover, MA, Sewanee, TN, and Waverly, IA.

Events and Calendars, Sky Maps and Occultations

Star, Moon, Comet and Meteorgazing at TAO in 2025

We enthusiastically invite visitors to attend our Public Stargaze events, held at our dark-sky site, the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) near Kingston, Tennessee. These events are intended especially for visitors, so our buildings and facilities will be open, and there will be astronomy talks as well as public skywatching.

In Jan-Jun 2025 we plan to hold fixed-calendar public Stargaze events on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These weekend events are especially appropriate for families. We also hold public special events, such as a “Full Moonrise,” with associated Moon Music, and the occasional comet watch. The annual Perseid Meteor watch in mid-August is especially popular.

The precise dates of many of these events depend on the local weather conditions, and cannot be specified *definitively* long in advance. As an approximate guide, see the TAOCalendar pages following. Once a date is finalized we usually confirm it through the ORION online message site ORION astronomy@groups.io. Likely and unlikely dates for TAO events may be inferred from the weather predictions at TAO by Clear Sky Charts (cleardarksky dot com) and Astrospheric (astrospheric dot com).

Please confirm event dates before proceeding to TAO.

In view of the rather challenging approach road to TAO, “Observatory Way,” first-time visitors should plan to arrive before dark. Driving instructions are given at: <https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/visit.htm>

Some instructions follow, since people may be unfamiliar with procedures for stargazing at a dark-sky site.

ORION members are invited to arrive early with their telescopes and mounts, to prepare for evening observing and to share refreshments. Please bring a red flashlight, or a headband with a red-light option.

Visitors who wish to acquire red lights or red-light headbands for observing may find them at many commercial amateur astronomy sites, such as [https:// www dot high pointscientific dot com](https://www.highpointscientific.com). The “Lepro LE” LED Headlamp, model 3200008, available from Amazon for about \$10 (Aug. 2024) is a personal favorite. This is rechargeable and has separate red and white led buttons, with several brightness settings. A caution: For amateur astronomy, brighter lights are NOT preferred, and WHITE lights are highly discouraged. Please use only red lights while the Stargaze is in progress.

Parking is available on site; on entering TAO **stay to the right**, and *please use the parking area below and right (Southwest) of the TAO buildings and observing area, near the treeline*. And **PLEASE NO HEADLIGHTS ON SITE.**

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of information as a primary goal of our organization. Visitors are welcome to coffee and other refreshments.

TAO Public Stargazing: A Note Regarding Scheduling and Access in 2025

In 2025 we will revert to an earlier schedule of having our Public Stargaze nights on every first and third Saturday. Of course this assumes good weather; if the weather is not suitable, a changed schedule will be announced on the group site [ORIONastronomy @ groups.io](mailto:ORIONastronomy@groups.io).

We decided that the previous (2024) schedule of a once-monthly Public Stargaze was insufficient, and having a Moon visible in some phase other than close to New gives our visitors an obvious and interesting object for viewing.

During Daylight Savings Time (mid-March through early November) we plan to hold our Public Stargaze events over the hours 8:00 pm - 11:00 pm. The planned Public Stargaze dates in Apr and Mar of 2025 are 5 Apr, 19 Apr, 3 May and 17 May.

If it is already dark when you arrive, please dim your headlights on the TAO grounds, follow the right branch of the access road, and park to the right of the TAO building, near the treeline.

Note: Parking in or near the elevated flat observing area at the front (East) of the TAO building is reserved for astronomers who are bringing their equipment.

Additional information for visitors may be found on the previous page and following two pages of this issue.

TAO Public Stargazes in April:

Sat 05 & 19 Apr 2025

Sat 05 Apr 2025

Sunset	8:05 pm
Civ dusk	8:31 pm
Ast dusk	9:33 pm
Moonrise	1:05 pm
Moonset*	4:15 am
	*06 Apr
Moon illum.	54%

Gibbous Moon during this event.

Sat 19 Apr 2025

Sunset	8:17 pm
Civ dusk	8:43 pm
Ast dusk	9:49 pm
Moonrise	1:56 am
Moonset	11:16 am
Moon illum.	75%

No Moon during this event.

Yet again there was a weather problem. The relevant forecasts anticipated evening conditions of 1/4 to 3/4 overcast, and my colleagues were pessimistic about even that. David Fields cancelled the Public Stargaze event, and in an online ORION Board discussion we settled on an astronomers' working session at TAO for that evening, nominally from 8:00 pm to 10:00 pm Eastern.

I arrived about 8:15 pm with two CPUs and the Arduino board, and found TAO totally overcast. We had about five ORION types present, these being Rob, David and myself, with two new members who had attended the 16 April ORION monthly meeting in Oak Ridge.

Although we officially had no Public Stargaze, just as last month we had several people stop by to ask us about our status and whether we might be available to help them with their interests in astronomy. In particular we had two father-and-son (I think) pairs, these being Justin and Braxton Bolton and Aaron and Caleb Chandler. We encouraged their participation (pending better weather), and recorded their contact information for future email communications.

I think this illustrates an important finding. Even when the night is overcast, and the Public Stargaze has officially been cancelled, we should still have ORION astronomers present to welcome any unexpected guests, and there are usually a few, who are potential new ORION members.

In view of the weather we did little observing. I experimented with using AnyDesk to communicate with a TAO CPU in the main building. Around 10 pm we had a sudden clearing of the sky to the West, so Rob was able to image Jupiter in the Meade. Only two Galilean moons were evident, and one was quite close to Jupiter's disk, which was a strikingly attractive image. Plans for setting up my Arduino inverse flasher synthetic asteroid occultation gadget (AIFSAOG) were not implemented, and we departed TAO about 11 pm.

During my seven years in the UK there was an organization called “The Not Terribly Good Club of Great Britain,” which was created especially for people who were notably lacking in some specific ability, such as telling jokes in formal public speeches. The club gave them an opportunity to practice their special lack of talent, occasionally in a competitive format. Their book “The Bumper Book of Boobs” made hilarious reading, with stories for example of someone who managed to set himself alight while starting an outdoor barbeque, and an actor in a Shakespearean play who refused to die at the appropriate time.

This takes me to the attempted TAO (private) Stargaze of Wed 23 April. Someone had suggested that date for a private (Board members) astronomy evening, should the weather be favorable. The usual evening-before discussion on What’sApp seemed undecided; I checked weather.com and found a thoroughly discouraging forecast for 23 Apr, with rain, overcast, and even thunderstorms, and argued against the proposed event. However the next day I heard that it was not cancelled, so I loaded my equipment and drove to TAO, arriving a bit late (8:20 pm); Art and Rob were already there. It was dark and cloudy, as anticipated, but no David, so we couldn’t get inside the TAO building. I had expected bad weather, but thought I could at least work on computer issues. However even this was not possible w/o David present to let us into the building. We tried our cell phones and discovered that David had decided that the weather had deteriorated, and cancelled his trip.

So, we three who were already at TAO stood around, made a few half-hearted jokes, and ate a few snacks. My peanut butter cookies from Krogers were quite good. We left about 8:45 pm, after a TAO residence time of perhaps 30 minutes. No stars, no blue patches in the sky, and no rain, just heavy clouds.

I submit this as our entry, entitled “The Not Terribly Good Stargaze of Wed 23 April 2025.”

As Rob noted, we were lucky not to have had any public visitors.

The Not Terribly Good Stargaze (cont.)

As a final view of this story, here are two nice pictures of 1) clouds at TAO, and 2) we folk who live under them. Upper, 8:41 pm Eastern, lower, Art and Rob, 8:27 pm Eastern, waiting for cookies.

TAO Public Stargazes in May:

Sat 03 & 17 May 2025

Sat 03 May 2025

Sunset	8:29 pm
Civ dusk	8:56 pm
Ast dusk	10:05 pm
Moonrise	12:00 noon
Moonset*	2:51 am
	*04 May
Moon illum.	39%

Crescent Moon during this event.

Sat 17 May 2025

Sunset	8:40 pm
Civ dusk	9:09 pm
Ast dusk	10:22 pm
Moonrise	00:40 am
Moonset	10:11 am
Moon illum.	79%

No Moon during this event.

This 1st Saturday Public Stargaze, planned for TAO on 03 May 2025, joined the long series of Stargaze events in 2025 that have succumbed to weather not appropriate for observing, or even for visitors to meet ORION people and sit through a lecture or two. This day turned out to have intense weather, with thunderstorms in the morning, heavy rains in the afternoon, and lighter rain in the evening. David Fields cancelled this Public Stargaze in the morning of 03 May 2025.

A possible substitute for 03 May 2025 at TAO was provided by a predicted Mars Occultation on the night of Mon-Tue 05-06 May 2025, with a practice session possible the evening before, Sun-Mon 4-5 May 2025. Although these two Mars events initially coincided with forecasts of at least partially clear skies, during the events themselves the weather was usually completely overcast, and only a few stalwart ORION people attended. (See the “Mars or Bust!” article later in this issue.)

A new series of monthly Stargaze events was initiated in Oak Ridge on Monday 03 Feb 2025, with the April event planned for Tue 08 Apr 2025. ORION plans to continue these monthly International Friendship Stargaze (IFS) events near the Peace Bell in A. K. Bissell Park.

This event is intended to bring enjoyment of the evening skies to people in the Oak Ridge, Clinton and surrounding areas who may find the 30-mile trip to TAO for one of our existing bimonthly 1st and 3rd Sat Public Stargaze events too onerous. Although the background light levels are rather high in the Oak Ridge area, it is still possible to view interesting objects such as the Moon, planets and stars through our telescopes.

Dates for future IFS Stargazes will be announced in the Trapezium, and on the ORIONastronomy at groups.io.

If the weather predictions for this date prove to be unfavorable, a change of plans will be announced on ORION astronomy at groups.io. It may be useful to follow the Oak Ridge area astronomy weather predictions on Clear Sky Charts (cleardark sky dot com) and Astrospheric (astrospheric dot com), to see whether the weather (smile emoji) for the planned date appears favorable in advance.

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of

information as a primary goal of our organization .

Please confirm the time and date of the event in advance before proceeding to the site, as these may have been changed.

Parking is available nearby, near the Oak Ridge Social Center building in the park; it's a short walk from there to the Peace Bell area. Since this is not a dark-sky location, no special lighting preparations are required, although those who have astronomy headlights may wish to bring them. Similarly, people who wish to bring their own outdoor seating, binoculars, telescopes and so forth are welcome to participate.

During Daylight Savings Time (DST), Apr-Oct IFS events, public telescope viewing will normally be from 9:00 - 10:30 pm, longer if there is public interest. Outside of DST, all these times will be an hour earlier. The times of this event are chosen with school age kiddies in mind.

The May IFS Stargaze also underwent several last minute changes of date and time, due primarily to the inclement weather. The previous week had demonstrated some very wet and rainy Springlike weather, so no possible IFS data appeared appropriate. David Fields chose Mon 12 May as a possibility, but this too proved to be overcast and rainy. In the forecasts the evening of 13 Tue appeared to be the best possibility for that week, so this was chosen (on the day before) as our May IFS day, starting at 9:00 pm. However the weather forecast deteriorated, and by 13 May morning the CSC forecast was for 50% overcast at that time. David Fields also noted that his intention was for the IFS to take place near the 1st quarter Moon, and 12 May was already Full Moon. So he cancelled the proposed 13 May event around noon on that date, and now looks forward to a June IFS event, with a beautiful first-quarter moon and nicer skies. In sha' Allah, as they say.

TAO Calendars

Jan-Jun 2025; Apr & May 2025

The principle public events for visitors at TAO are the **Public Stargazes**, held at TAO during 2025 on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These are listed in the “**Public Fixed Events**” **TAO Calendar** for a six month period, currently Jan-Jun 2025. This appears on the page following.

Additional notable events will be included in monthly “**Special Events**” **TAO Calendars**. These include public events that do not have a fixed date long in advance, such as the **International Friendship Stargaze** in Oak Ridge, and special TAO events such as **Asteroid Occultations, Meteor Showers, Full Moonrises, Lunar (and other) Eclipses, Comet Watches**, and perhaps the occasional musical event.

These “Special Events” calendars for the current and subsequent months appear after the six-month “Public Fixed Events” calendar.

The facilities in the TAO buildings onsite will be open to the public during the “Public Fixed Events,” and will also usually be available when TAO is open to the public for some of the “Special Events.” **Please inquire regarding whether TAO will be open to the public for any “Special Event” you may wish to attend, since some may be restricted.** We will of course always try to accommodate enthusiastic visitors.

We recommend checking a TAO website such as **ORIONAstronomy @ groups.io** before visiting, to confirm that listed events will proceed as planned; weather conditions for example may require a cancellation or change of date.

TAO Calendar Public Fixed Events

Jan-Jun 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 04 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Feb 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Feb 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Mar 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Mar 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 05 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 19 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 03 May 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 17 May 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 07 Jun 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight
Sat 21 Jun 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight

These 2025 TAO Public Events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter and Spring, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAOCalendar Special Events

May 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 03 May 2025	<small>cancelled</small> 	1 st Sat Public Stargaze	9:00 pm	11:00 pm
Tue 06 May 2025		Mars occults 9.1 mag TYC 1398-00275-1 midpt <i>ca.</i> 00:45 am EDT	09:00 pm 05 May	01:30 am 06 May
Mon 12 May 2025		Full Moon 02:56 pm Eastern		
Tue 13 May 2025	<small>cancelled</small> 	International Friendship Stargaze (Oak Ridge)	9:00 pm	10:30 pm
Sat 17 May 2025		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Wed 21 May 2025		Asteroid Occultation 73857 Hitaneichi 01:24:24 am Eastern	8:00 pm Tue 20 May	2:00 am Wed 21 May
Mon 26 May 2025		New Moon 11:02 pm Eastern		

TAOCalendar Special Events

Jun 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 07 Jun 2025	★	1 st Sat Public Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Ddd nn Jun 2025	★	International Friendship Stargaze (Oak Ridge)	9:00 pm	10:30 pm
Wed 11 Jun 2025	○	Full Moon 03:44 am Eastern		
Sat 21 Jun 2025	★	3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Wed 25 Jun 2025	●	New Moon 06:31 am Eastern		

The evening Sky Map for May 2025 from skymaps.com.

The Evening Sky Map

FREE* EACH MONTH FOR YOU TO EXPLORE, LEARN & ENJOY THE NIGHT SKY

Sky Calendar - May 2025

Follow us on Bluesky
skymaps.com/bsky/

- Asteroid 4 Vesta at opposition at 12h UT. Mag. 5.7.
- Moon near M35 Cluster at 12h UT (51° from Sun, evening sky).
- Moon, Mars and Beehive Cluster (M44) within circle 2.6° diameter at 1h UT (evening sky). Mag. 1.0.
- First Quarter Moon at 13:52 UT.
- Mars 0.6° NNE of Beehive Cluster (M44) at 14h UT (evening sky). Mag. 1.0.
- Moon near Regulus at 21h UT (evening sky).
- Eta Aquariid meteor shower peaks. Most active for 7 days around this date. Associated with Comet Halley. Very fast, bright meteors, up to 50 per hour. Best seen from the tropics and southern hemisphere a few hours before dawn. Viewing conditions are ideal in 2025 for this major meteor shower.
- Moon near Spica at 6h UT (evening sky). Occultation visible from southern Pacific Ocean.
- Moon at apogee (farthest from Earth) at 1h UT (distance 406,244km; angular size 29.4').
- Full Moon at 16:57 UT.
- Moon near Antares at 2h UT (morning sky). Occultation visible from Argentina, Chile, Uruguay and the Falkland Islands.
- Asteroid 3 Juno at opposition at 6h UT. Mag. 10.1.
- Last Quarter Moon at 11:59 UT.
- Moon near Saturn at 16h UT (morning sky). Mag. 1.1.
- Moon near Venus at 19h UT (morning sky). Mag. -4.4.
- Moon at perigee (closest to Earth) at 1:32 UT (distance 359,022km; angular size 33.3').
- New Moon at 3:03 UT. Start of lunation 1267.
- Moon near Jupiter at 14h UT (20° from Sun, evening sky). Mag. -1.9.
- Moon near M35 Cluster at 22h UT (25° from Sun, evening sky).
- Mercury at superior conjunction with the Sun at 4h UT (not visible). The innermost planet passes into the evening sky.
- Moon near Beehive Cluster (M44) at 11h UT (evening sky).

More sky events and links at <https://Skymaps.com/skycalendar/>
 All times in Universal Time (UT). (USA Eastern Daylight Time - UT - 4 hours.)

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 Recommended Telescopes & Products at: skymaps.com/astro/

NORTHERN HEMISPHERE MAY 2025

SKY MAP SHOWS HOW THE NIGHT SKY LOOKS

EARLY MAY 10 PM
 LATE MAY 9 PM
 (All 1 hour for Twilight Ending)
 SKY MAP DRAWN FOR A LATITUDE OF 40° NORTH AND IS SUITABLE FOR LATITUDES UP TO 15° NORTH OR SOUTH OF THIS

- Symbols**
- Galaxy ☁
 - Double Star ●●
 - Variable Star ●
 - Diffuse Nebula ☁
 - Planetary Nebula ○
 - Open Star Cluster ○
 - Globular Star Cluster ⊕

Star Magnitudes ●●●●●
 -1 0 1 2 3 4

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Note: a nice interactive sky chart from Sky and Telescope may be found at the link <https://skyandtelescope.org/interactive-sky-chart/>

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana:

TAO, 14 Apr 2025.

- Ted Barnes

While recently checking the predictions of the IOTA program Occult Watcher for asteroid occultations that would be visible from TAO, I was very surprised to note mention of an asteroid that I had encountered in a previous TAO occultation. And not just any TAO occultation; the very first one we had attempted, successfully, to observe and record, very early on the Sunday morning of 22 Oct 2023.

At this first TAO occultation, asteroid 785 Zwetana was predicted to occult a “bright” 9.5 magnitude star in Cetus, TYC 4687-01288-1, for a predicted maximum duration of 3.28 secs. TAO was close to the predicted shadow center line, so something like 3 secs duration could actually be expected. The predicted time of the occultation midpoint was a painful 02:43:05 am Eastern. The asteroid itself would be a much fainter mag 14.0. This asteroid is of the uncommon Tholen class M, implying probably metallic.

This first TAO occultation is described in detail on pp.16-29 of the 17 Nov 2023 issue of the Trapezium. All the familiar difficulties of an occultation are described there, including surprisingly gusty winds before midnight, various appalling clouds, and a 43% illuminated Moon, which fortunately set at 00:26 am Eastern. Another difficulty was that the target star would cross the Meridian about 01:20 am, so I had to do some creative late night star hopping to avoid crossing the Meridian with the telescope.

Remarkably the troubled skies cleared considerably around 02:30 am, and after a dramatic countdown, at 02:42:58 pm Eastern I began recording 200 100ms frames at a maximum camera gain of 570. (The camera being a ZWO ASI294MCP.)

During this first occultation we never saw the target star vanish from the CPU monitor, so we initially had no doubt that we had failed to observe the occultation. Similarly, Larry and D.R. had failed to observe an extinction of the target star, which they had been watching through the Meade LX200. After receiving consolations from various attendees, we returned home, and I examined the 200 100ms frames that the camera had captured. I was stunned to find that the target star went out at frame 25, and reappeared at frame 42: ***We Had Recorded The Occultation!*** Our recorded duration of 1.8(1) secs was much shorter than anticipated; when I submitted my positive observer’s report to IOTA, Steve Preston (who had earlier recorded one 785 Zwetana occultation but missed a second) told me that he suspected that this asteroid had an irregular shape, and my observed short duration could be explained accordingly. So, as you see we really had a history with this asteroid, and should certainly try to record this new occultation.

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

The first observation of an asteroid occultation at TAO, on 22 Oct 2023, involving the asteroid 785 Zwetana, then in the constellation Cetus. This image was captured not long before that occultation. The event took place at $\text{Alt} = 45.5^\circ$ and $\text{Azi} = 210.2^\circ$, about halfway up from the horizon to vertical (the zenith), and to the SSW.

2023 caption:

Agatha (L) and Ted intently watch a SharpCap screen at TAO as the predicted time of 2:43:05 am Eastern, Sun 22 Oct 2023 for the occultation of the star TYC 4687-01288-1 by asteroid (785) Zwetana approaches. The OTA is at upper left. *Image by Allan Poole*

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

In many ways this return occultation by 785 Zwetana on 14 Apr 2025 was less favorable for the observer than our original 22 Oct 2023 event. In this new event 785 Zwetana would be much lower in the sky, at an altitude of only Alt 13.6° , which made it much more susceptible to low clouds. (Previously it was at Alt 45.5° .) Also, the new event would be in the WNW, at Azi = 301.2° , which necessitated a search for a new setup location. At my usual setup site near the tall dome this Alt, Azi combination was blocked by the TAO building. In 2023 the original event was at (Alt, Azi) = (45.5° , 210.2°), to the SSW and well above the treeline. Another serious problem was the Moon; in 2023 it had set about 2 hrs before the occultation, whereas in 2025 it was a Full Moon, 100% illuminated, at (Alt, Azi) = (35.3° , 168.5°). Although the Moon was 114° from the event when the 2025 occultation took place, it was still very bright, and there was considerable background scattered moonlight.

For this event I was accompanied by Beth Bredeson, my son-in-law's sister, on her second trip to TAO (see following images). We arrived about 7:00 pm and began looking for a good place to set up, given the low altitude and awkward direction of this 2025 event (it was not visible from most of the TAO concrete pads). Although the Northern edge of the new far pad appeared possible, the two cell-phone compasses available didn't agree all that well, and it was unclear whether 300° Azimuth would be easily visible to the right of the large tree near the TAO building. (Someone still needs to check the range of Azi visible from the new pads.)

To be sure of seeing the region around Azi = 300° I decided to follow my original plan, and set up on the sundial pad just West of the TAO building. We soon had regrets; there were three ant nests around the concrete sundial, and they responded energetically to being disturbed. Of course no one had ant repellent. Also the ground had a significant downhill E \rightarrow W slope, so using my portable CPU-and-monitor table there was awkward.

Once we got the 8" Orion Ritchey-Chretien Astrograph set up I looked for Polaris to align the mount platform, but this was nontrivial; it was misty, and the faintish star in the sky that might be Polaris wasn't convincing as such. Eventually after taking a stroll around the grounds I convinced myself that this really was Polaris, but it was awkwardly close to the outer (West-facing) leaves of that one TAO Tree. (Somebody stop me! – Jim Carry, "Mask.")

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

JPL/Horizons diagram showing the inner solar system and the position of 785 Zwetana at the time of the occultation of 14 Apr 2025.

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

I usually make my most impressive mistake when I am setting up my telescope WHILE telling young people and visitors what I am doing. During this event I was trying to be helpful to Beth by explaining what I was doing, instead of just concentrating on doing it. Thus for example I showed Beth how when you turn on the telescope orienting program CPWI, you have an option of changing your longitude and latitude coordinates on the Earth, which should be done with every significant move, such as the move from my home site LRO in Clinton to TAO. After some shuffling through index cards I found my list of coordinates, and replaced the LRO values by the TAO coordinates.

Next I began trying to align my telescope with the sky, as shown on a CPWI stellar map appropriate for our date, time and location. But something was wrong. I tried to slew to a few bright stars in Ursa Major, which CPWI showed below and left of Polaris. But my slews didn't take me to any likely looking stars. I COULD see Capella, and tried to reach it using short steps, but Auriga was not in the right location on the CPWI map.

It was still twilight, so I started to wonder whether I had been wrong in my assumption about which star was Polaris. I took a long stroll to the South and then East, to the front of the TAO building, where there was no doubt about which star was Polaris, and also that Ursa Major was up and to the right of Polaris. Something was clearly very wrong with my computer's settings. I initially thought I had it set to the wrong time, like a coming event, but a check showed that the time was correct. Then I realized that I had input the longitude to CPWI incorrectly; instead of 84 degrees, I should have started with -84 degrees, telling CPWI that this was West Longitude, not East! I had given CPWI Earth coordinates of some location in Western China, near the Gobi desert. No wonder the star positions shown by CPWI were crazy. It only took me about an hour to figure out this error; I hope Beth learned from my mistake. (I think she did; later she asked how soon we would be attaching the telescope weights, whereas I had actually forgotten them, and had already set up the OTA atop the mount without any weights.)

After this bad start I was able to align the telescope fairly quickly, and we were soon looking at stars in the vicinity of the coming event, recording the star field around the target star, setting up guiding, and waiting for the time of the occultation.

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

OW Cloud (785) Zwetana occults TYC 2442-00543-1 on 14 Apr 2025

This Occult Watcher image shows the predicted local trajectory of the shadow of **785 Zwetana (50 km diam)** on the Earth's surface. At TAO's position one would expect the max duration to be reduced by about a factor of $\sqrt{1-(18.6/25)^2} = 0.67$, assuming a spherical asteroid. This would reduce the predicted **max duration** of 2.4 secs on the centerline to **1.6 secs** at TAO's location.

Challenges were a **100% illum Full Moon**, a **messy sky** unlike the clear one predicted by CSC and Astrospheric, an **unfamiliar tilted location** with **ants**, **poor seeing**, **2am**, and a **low elevation**.

Prediction

Last Updated: **11/Apr/25, 03:14 UT**
 Data Sources: **Horizons/GaiaDR3**
 Error (path widths): **0.027**
 Err. Ellipse: **0.002" x 0.0004"**
 Err. Basis: **Known errors**

Computed By: **OWC**
 Orbit Date: **09 Apr 2025 (JPL#102)**
 Error in time: **0.2 sec**
 Err. Ellipse PA: **80°**
 OWC Id: **2256731**

Event

From: **05:39:13 UT**
 Combined Mag: **10.50**
 Mag Drop (V): **3.20**
 Shadow Width: **70.1 km**
 Solar Elong.: **80°**

To: **05:46:32 UT**
 Max Duration: **2.4 sec**
 Mag Drop (R): **2.89**
 Moon Phase: **99% sunlit**
 Moon Elong.: **114°**

Target Star

Name: **TYC 2442-00543-1**
 Constellation: **Gemini**
 Diameter:
 RUWE: **1.05**
 Gaia SourceId: **891250587738308864**
 RA [ICRS]: **07^h 06^m 28^s.0391**
 Dec [ICRS]: **+33° 44' 06".693**

V mag: **11.06**
 R mag: **10.58**
 B mag: **11.37**
 Flags:
 Gaia Flags:
 RA [aprrt]: **07^h 08^m 07^s.2673**
 Dec [aprrt]: **+33° 41' 53".346**

Object

Name: **(785) Zwetana**
 Diameter: **50.4 ± 2.4 km (Occult)**
 Distance: **2.2813 au**
 Motion RA: **44.78 °/hr**
 Moons: **0**

Class: **Main-belt Asteroid**
 Diameter (augm): **30.46 mas**
 Mag: **14.2** 📶
 Motion Dec: **-9.06 °/hr**
 Rings: **0**

Alt @ Azi = 13.6° @ 301°

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

One of the unexpected challenges encountered in recording the occultation by 785 Zwetana was the sky. Both CSC and Astrospheric had predicted clear skies for TAO, with a hint of cloud around 10 pm Eastern. In practice the sky was populated by occasional small puffy cumulus clouds and layered dark stratus near the horizon that could immediately have invalidated the recording of the occultation. There were also misty clouds scattering light from the nearly 100% illuminated Moon, giving background noise to the images captured.

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

Setup at the Sundial
Beth Bredeson
TAO, 8:50 pm 13 Apr 2025 EDT

Participating in this event was Beth Bredeson, sister of the Editor's son-in-law. This was Beth's second visit to TAO, and her first occultation experience. She maintained an admirable stoicism throughout the event, despite the high density of ants on the sundial platform, the awkward tilted table and tilted ground surface generally, the presence of a rich variety of late Spring flying insects, and an inadvertent demonstration by the Editor of how a simple minus sign error in a longitude entry in CPWI can convince your computer and the CPWI onscreen sky display that you are actually somewhere in Western China. (It only took me about an hour to find that error.) And later, things became really problematic.

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

Moon Alt @ Azi = 35° @ 169°
Illum. = 100%

Event Alt @ Azi = 13.6° @ 302°

A sky chart generated using TheSkyX showing the location of the occultation, near the Gemini-Auriga border. An artificial Alt = 0° desert horizon is included. The sky extends to approx Alt = 40°, and the horizon runs from approx 260° to 330°. The bright Full Moon is out of field, high and 90° left beyond the left boundary. The most notable object in this misty early morning moonlit Western sky was the linear triad of (L to R) Mars, Pollux and Castor.

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

A 4-minute stack of the field, about 2 hours before the main event.

A stack of 240 1sG480 full-field frames (1920x1200 px), captured at midpt 11:57 pm Eastern, 13 Apr 2025. Stars to 18th mag can be identified here. The brightest star (at right) is g-mag 7.5 star HD 53314, with a 9.5 g-mag “partner” below and left. At midfield left is the second brightest g-mag 8.1 star HD 53531. The g-mag 11.2 target star TYC 2442-00543-1 appears between two red dashes. The much fainter mag-14.2 approaching occulting asteroid 785 Zwetana is also visible nearby, see the image three pages following for its location. Attempted stacks using 2s and 4s frames were “washed out” by moonlight.

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

An expected field of view at the predicted time of the occultation, generated using TheSkyX. This shows the full field of view (1920x1200 pixels, green rectangle) anticipated for the QHY174MGPS camera attached to the 8" Orion Ritchey-Chretien Astrograph, both used during this event. **785 Zwetana** appears reassuringly superimposed on the **target star TYC 2442-00543-1**, at the J2000.0 coordinates RA 07 06 27.99, Dec +33 44 07.4. Recent predictions for the event time midpoint varied from 01:46:18 to 01:46:20 am Eastern.

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

TYC 2442-00543-1, $m_g = 11.2$

Aladin DSS2 image of target star TYC 2442-00543-1 and field

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

Stack of 240 1sG480 frames, 1920x1200 px,
midpt 11:57 pm EDT, 13 Apr 2025

target star and asteroid indicated

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

TAO, 00:25am Eastern 14 Apr 2025
Showing PHD2 guiding (L) and SharpCap (R) data screens.

SharpCap with **live images + gps timestamp**
and selecting a **tiny 256x128 px ROI !**

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

Full field and 256x128 ROI (ROI = a tiny “region of interest” in midfield, shown on the large display)

1:21:36 before captures. Alles in Ordnung.

The target star is visible as a cluster of pixels in the bottom left quadrant of the inner circle, maintained in position in the ROI by the guiding program.

Check occasionally, and continue to wait ...

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

The target star (near the center) vanished at this time.

U 042433

4 mins before event ... crash!

No Star!

Just "white noise."

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

U 042433

Emergency responses:

Increase screen capture frame size from 256x128 to 1024x768.
Capture 100 200ms frames starting at 01:46:10 am as planned.
Hope for the best. Hope we capture something relevant!

n.b. It was a small cloud. The star reappeared anyway.
But now I have no idea which faint star in the field is the target star.

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

TYC 2442-00543-1

Starting at UT 05:46.10.2821105 I captured 100 200ms frames of size 1024x768 px. The transitions of the target star TYC 2442-00543-1 to eclipsed frames (44-45) and back to unclipped frames (51-52) are shown. (Extreme brightness and contrast enhancements.)

These imply an event midpoint at TAO of UT 01:46:19.8(1) and a duration of 1.4(1) secs. These values were reported to IOTA on 15 Apr 2025.

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

Observation was: Positive

Asteroid Occultation Report Form
All times MUST be reported using UTC

V5.6.11

Year: 2025 Month: April Day: 14 Predicted Time (UTC): 05 : 46 : 18
hh mm ss

Asteroid: # 785 Name: Zwetana Star: TYC 2442-00543-1
Catalog Format Number

Observer(s): Ted Barnes Email: ted.barnes2@yahoo.com
Mailing Address: 182 Burley Nelson Lane Phone: 2404839608
City, State, Country: Clinton, Tennessee, USA Fax:

Lucky Star or RIO-TNO Prediction? No

Observing Location: Rockwood, Tennessee, USA <---(nearest City/Town, with State/Country only)

Location: Latitude: 35 49 58.70 deg mm ss.zzz N Longitude: 84 37 04.30 deg mm ss.zzz W Elevation: 324 m Datum: Other

Telescope: Aperture: 20.0 cm f/ratio: 8.0 Magnification: Type: Newtonian

Timing: GPS - other linking Method: Video with frame analysis Asteroid visible before/during occ? yes
Timing Device: Other - Specify in Comments OTE Used: Other - Specify in Comments

Detector: Model/Type: Other - List in Comments Video Format: FITS Images Exposure Integration: Other Unit: Fields Other Detector related info: QHY174MGPS

Conditions: Clouds: Thin cloud < 2 Stability: Strong flickering Other conditions: 100% illum Moon, turbulent

Observations:

	Times			Accuracy	PE	Remark
	hh	mm	ss.zzz	Enter Confidence Level Error Bars In Boxes Below		
Started Observing:	05	46	10.282			
Manually-Corrected Disappearance:	05	46	19.100			
Corrected Disappearance:	05	46	19.100	0.1		Difficult condition; 100% illum Moon, turbulent seeing. Captured 100 200ms frames using SharpCap, QHY174MGPS frames timestamped with gps. Estimated errors are +/- 0.1 sec, as +/- half a 200ms bin. Recorded duration 1.4 sec (D and R times entered at left.)
Corrected Reappearance:	05	46	20.500	0.1		Event midpt time 05:46:19.8(1) UT. This is my 2nd encounter with 785 Zwetana. Telescope an
Manually-Corrected Reappearance:	05	46	20.500			ORION 8" Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph. (n.b. Images are jpgs not FITS.) Occasional small
Stopped Observing:	05	46	30.289			nearly invisible clouds blocked images. PHD2 guiding. 100 200ms 1024x768 frames saved.
				Units are in Seconds 68.3% 95.0% 99.7%	< 35% confidence level will be reported to IOTA	<input type="checkbox"/> Was this a Miss?

2nd star Select Yes if this report is for the second star of a double. S/N = (if known)

Additional Comments: challenging conditions. Full Moon, backscatter, and a few small irregular wispy clouds. n.b. Re duration, OW said 2.4 sec max. Since we were 18.6 km from centerline and shad radius = 25.0 km, assuming a spherical asteroid we expect 2.4 secs * sqrt(1-(18.6/25.0)^2) = 1.6 secs. Consistent w obs of 1.4(1) secs.

Report prepopulated by IOTA Reporting Add-in for OW ver.1.9

Email report to: reports@asteroidoccultation.com
If available please include a Tangra or Limovie CSV file of the light curve data with the report.

The final report on the occultation, submitted to IOTA on 15 Apr 2025.

The Terrible Return of Asteroid 785 Zwetana (cont.)

DARK STAR AWARD

*Occultation of star TYC 2442-00543-1 by 785 Zwetana
at TAO, 01:46:20 am Eastern 14 Apr 2025*

Awardee: B. Bredeson

Mars or Bust !

TAO Planetary Occultation Observation Attempt of 06 May 2025.

- Ted Barnes

1 281 037 022

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

Martian Flash ...

Next notable occultation at TAO:

Tue 06 May 2025, 00:44 am Eastern

(After midnight, night of Mon/Tue 5-6 May 2025.)

The magnitude **9.1** star **TYC 1398-00275-1**
will be occulted by *The Planet Mars*, magnitude 1.0.

In Cancer, Alt@Azi = 19°@281°

Predicted midpoint at TAO 00:44:56 am Eastern

Predicted duration **322.2 seconds** +/- **2.5 secs**

J2000.0 coords: RA = 08 42 21.55, Dec +20 10 53.6

Moon Alt @ Azi = 37° @ 256°

Moon distance alas only 27°

Moon illumination 66%

Mars will be much too bright for us to observe the full occultation itself,
But we will follow the approach and exit stages,
ca. 12:00 – 1:30 am Eastern.

<https://cloud.occultwatcher.net/event/1586-P4M00-123421-649262-T00275-1/2338090>

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

A chart generated using TheSkyX showing the position of Mars in Cancer at the time of the occultation, 12:45 am Eastern, 6 May 2025. Mars is close to both α Cnc and the Beehive Cluster.

Mars or Bust !

(cont.)

Much of my observing now involves asteroid occultations, since these enjoyable, challenging and exciting observations require considerable advance planning, preparation of star charts, learning more about the asteroids (we know about over 1.5 million of them), and interpreting the exciting Olympian prognostications extracted from various weather services.

To see what asteroid occultations may be observed from TAO (or other sites) one simply follows the output of the program Occult Watcher (OW), and attempts to find events that have a sufficiently bright target star (mag at least 12), and are not anticipated to take place at too uncivilized an hour (2 am or earlier, please). One also watches the occulting body to see if it is relatively bright for an asteroid (like 10th mag), or is a tiny body that one might not see at all (like 19th mag), but for the target star vanishing for a fraction of a second.

Occasionally one finds a truly novel entry, such as an occultation by the planet Mars (mag a blinding 1.0) of a much fainter background star. In this case OW noted that Mars would occult the 9.1 magnitude star TYC 1398-00275-1 (type F3V) in Cancer on Tue 6 May 2025, at a fairly civilized estimated midtime of 00:44:56 Eastern, for a max duration of 5.4 mins.

This event was an inversion of many of the familiar aspects of recording asteroid occultations. First, as a plus, the time scales were much longer than for a normal occultation, 5 minutes instead of a few seconds. Second, and this is a killer, the occulting body is MUCH brighter than the target star. In this case, the 8 magnitude difference implies that Mars is about 1600 times brighter than the star being occulted. The final impossibility is that we would in principle like to follow the target star all the way down to extinction, when its light is intercepted by the Martian surface. (And we would also ideally like to observe the target star's reappearance, on the other side of Mars. And that's presumably an indication of the pony we will receive on Christmas morning.)

The scale of difficulty we will encounter is nicely illustrated on the following page, which shows Arcturus (a convenient bright red object) and a nearby star (CN Boo, about 6 magnitudes fainter), in a crop from the DSS2 sky survey on the Aladin website. One can see that the fainter star can indeed (just) be identified, but in this case it is at a separation from Arcturus of about 17' (17 [arcmin]). In comparison the angular distance from the center of Mars to its horizon is only about 3.2" (3.2 [arcsec]), about 320x smaller than the angular distance shown here from CN Boo to Arcturus.

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

In this DSS2 image from Aladin one can appreciate the difficulty of observing a fainter star (here mag 6.0 CN Boo) against a much brighter object, in this case the star Arcturus (α Boo, $m_v = -0.05$). In the Martian occultation the target star is 8 magnitudes fainter than the occulting body (about 6 times fainter than in the image above), and should ideally be followed to the Martian surface, which is only about 3.2'' (3.2 [arcsecs]) from the center of the Martian disk, about 1/320 of the 17' CN Boo - Arcturus separation seen here. Clearly observing a Martian occultation of even a moderately faint star will likely be a very difficult task.

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

no filter
QHY174M
1sG300

23.8' x 14.9'
1920 x 1200

First let's ignore the many impossibilities of recording the full Martian occultation, and see how much of it we might actually expect to record. With our usual occultation equipment, an 8" ORION RC reflector and QHY174MGPS camera, here taking a 1 sec exposure with a modest gain of 300 to reduce image blooming (1sG300), a single raw image of Arcturus appears as above. This 1920 x 1200 px full-field image has an f.o.v. of 23.8' x 14.9'. The radius of the white "light disk" of Arcturus is approx 22", so we might be able to follow a star to about that angular distance from the center of Mars' disk, about 7 Mars radii. Reassuringly, a mag 9.6 star (fainter than the 6 May 2025 Mars occultation's target star!) appears in this image at lower left; this is Tycho 1472:1433.

Reducing the image to 1sG200, the radius of the central light disk falls to about 17", and the mag 9.6 star remains visible. So, we might be able to follow the target star in to something like 5 Mars radii.

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

2025 04 29 01:30:39:8059440 Z

H β filter
QHY174M
1sG300

23.8' x 14.9'
1920 x 1200

Another potentially useful technique is to pass the light from the event through a filter that will lower the brightness of Mars much more than the target star. To test one possibility we attached a 2" blue-green H β narrowband filter to the front of the camera, and captured several images for comparison with no-filter images. The raw H β 1sG300 image is shown above, and Arcturus' light disk is indeed considerably reduced relative to the no-filter case on the previous page; the H β 1sG300 light disk radius is about 15", whereas the no-filter 1sG300 radius was about 22". Again reducing the gain, the H β 1sG200 light disk radius falls to about 10", about 3 Mars radii. Unfortunately the 9.6 mag test star near Arcturus was also significantly dimmed by the H β filter, and the star was only visible after stretching the brightness and contrast. It is not yet clear whether this filter will be useful in observing an actual Mars occultation.

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

The timing of this Mars occultation proved to be somewhat obscure. OW gave an event midpoint time at TAO of 00:44:56 Eastern on Tue 6 May 2025, and a maximum duration (for TAO? for anywhere?) of 322 secs with an error of 2.5 secs, but the disappear and reappear times were not quoted. Several programs such as TheSkyX and Stellarium do show the event, but differ by several minutes regarding the actual disappear and reappear times. In this situation I decided it was best to try to generate my own estimates.

I assumed that the JPL Horizons Mars ephemeris data was the most reliable, and generated a table of Martian center RA and Dec coordinates as observed from TAO for 04:00 am - 5:30 am UT, Tue 6 May 2025, at one minute intervals, the shortest JPL provides. These are quoted by JPL to one place accuracy in Dec secs and two place accuracy in RA secs. The J2000.0 coordinates of the target star, RA 8 42 21.6135121 and Dec +20 10 53.959177, were taken from Gaia. These were used with the spherical trigonometry identity quoted in the Astronumerology section,

$$\cos(\Theta_{12}) = \sin(\theta_1)\sin(\theta_2) + \cos(\theta_1)\cos(\theta_2)\cos(\phi_1 - \phi_2)$$

to give values for the target star – Mars center separation angle (Θ_{12}) as a function of time. These are plotted with xmgrace below, and enlarged on the page following.

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

An enlargement of the JPL Horizons ephemeris data close to the deepest point of occultation. (The finest resolution available for this data was one minute.) The red dashed line (in this graph and on the previous page) shows a Martian horizon angle of $3.181''$ from the planet's center, estimated from the Martian distance (JPL) and a mean Martian radius of 3390 [km].

This data gives estimated disappearance and reappearance times at TAO of 00:43:12 and 00:48:07 Eastern, for a local duration of 295 secs. A rough interpolation suggests a closest approach time of about 00:45:38 Eastern, with a nominal closest approach to the Martian disk center (not visible of course) of about $1.3''$.

Mars occultation 6 May 2025 00:00 - 01:30 Eastern
detail: using JPL Horizons data

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

Since the various “app” predictions for the event times differ considerably, by about a minute or two, it may be possible to test them observationally by recording the Mars – target star separations accurately at several times during the approach and then during the separation, when the target star is still well outside the planet’s “bloomed” light disk in the images. These results can be linearly extrapolated to give our best estimate for the event midpoint time, where these extrapolations meet.

Of course we need to test our Mars image filter results, with various filters, exposures and gains, during a test run at TAO. The weather appeared favorable for Sun-Mon night 4-5 May 2025, so this was chosen as our trial run. An image of the sky at 11:00 pm from TheSkyX is shown below. The star at lower left is mag 8.5, comparable to the target star.

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

This “TheSkyX” image shows the lovely field predicted for the Mars occultation of 6 May 2025. Of course at magnitude 1.0 Mars dominates the image; we might expect to see 8.6 mag Tycho 1398:240 at right, but not much more. The “tail” of three 13th mag stars would presumably be washed out by Mars. Another problem I have not even mentioned is a gibbous moon at a distance of only 27°, and the low target star position of Alt@Azi = 19°@281°. Well after all, this is a first attempt.

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

If we assume that we are only following the system for a short period of time, so the motion of Mars can be accurately described using Cartesian coordinates (with distances in [arcsec], a.k.a. asec or " "), with a fixed stellar background. After a suitable rotation we can represent the system as follows:

By inspection the angular distance from the target star to the center of the Martian disk will vary with time as

$$\Theta_{12} = \left(b^2 + v^2(t-t_0)^2 \right)^{1/2}$$

where b is the angular impact parameter [asec], v is the angular rate of motion of Mars across the field of background stars [asec/sec], and t_0 is the event midpoint time. Fitting this simple form to our data will give estimates for b and t_0 . The (assumed constant) angular velocity v of Mars against the stellar background can be extracted from our ephemeris. We anticipated observing the approach and departure of Mars and the target star for something like 11:00 pm – 12:30 am Eastern and 1:00 am – 1:45 am Eastern on 5-6 May, weather permitting, to provide considerable Θ_{12} data to compare with the theoretical approach and departure curves on pp. 58-59. We did not expect to be able to see the faint target star during approx 12:30 am – 1:00 am Eastern, well before and well after it crossed the Martian horizon, due to the proximity of the very bright Martian disk.

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

Weather issues:

Of course the weather is frequently a concern for astronomical events, and the Mars occultation at TAO was not an exception. A week in advance one could believe that there was a possibility that the nights of 4-5 May 2025 (practice night) and 5-6 May 2025 (event night) might both have useable skies. However these predictions deteriorated with time. On the practice night the skies were overcast and turbulent on arrival, and the prediction that they might clear for some time from *ca.* 11:00 pm proved to be unrealistic.

View of the rather turbulent skies visible to the West of TAO at 8:18 pm Eastern, on our nominal practice night, Sun-Mon 4-5 May 2025.

Fortunately there were other important activities at TAO that merited our attention; one was using the AnyDesk software to allow two-way communication between TAO computers and external computers, which will be important for recording future events using remote telescope techniques. We made great progress in setting up remote telescope access at TAO that evening. (See the “Shop Talk” section, p.68.)

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

Event Night, Mon-Tue 5-6 May 2025:

Mon 05 May 2025

One notable disadvantage of not having had a clear sky for our nominal practice night of 4-5 May 2025 was that we had not yet tested the various Mars filters for their effectiveness in reducing the brightness of the Martian disk. So, we started this evening with various untested filters, hoping for a clear sky interval before the event to test their effectiveness.

Sunset	8:31 pm
Civ dusk	8:59 pm
Ast dusk	10:09 pm
Moonrise	2:10 pm
Moonset*	3:48 am
	*6 May
Moon illum.	59%

The predictions of our three usual forecast services for % overcast by hour are given below. You can see why we were motivated to at least attempt to capture an early phase of the Mars occultation on 5-6 May. Alas there was little consensus in the predictions, and only a rough correlation with the actual weather. The latter was not useable for observing.

<u>Time Eastern</u>	<u>% overcast:</u>	Astrospheric	CSC	ClearOutside	reality
7 pm 5 May		27	70	50	
8		6	0	54	
9		7	0	41	clear
10		2	0	48	overcast
11		11	20	60	overcast
midnight 5-6 May		33	20	73	overcast
1 am 6 May		58	60	84	overcast

In terms of accuracy the forecasts were “not terribly good.” We arrived at TAO (setup area) to a clear sky about 9:00 pm. However around 10 pm a close to 100% blanket overcast arrived, and except for occasional glimpses of a few stars and a Werewolf Moon, the sky didn’t significantly improve throughout the evening. I used a rough alignment to approximately orient my system, and glimpsed Polaris a few times, so I could tell that it was roughly correct. I had problems with my laser, OTA and guidescope all being surprisingly somewhat misaligned, so I spent some of the evening trying to align them using a distant ground-sited white light source to the West. Since I was missing a camera extension needed to focus my small-pixel ASI183MCP (the extension was still in the van, I incorrectly assumed I had left it at home), even this simple exercise was difficult.

So, in summary, *this was a Bust*, largely due to two successive days of overcast weather. **On the event night of 5-6 May 2025 we captured no images of Mars, or the target star, or the associated star fields**, and were not even able to properly align our telescopes. At least we can say that **we made the effort, and did considerable work in preparation, which may be useful for future planetary occultation observation attempts.**

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

Event Night, Mon-Tue 5-6 May 2025:

As we at least knew when the event would take place, and where Mars was in the sky behind the clouds, we brave few (Rob, Beth and Ted) gathered outside about 12:35 am on 6 May 2025, gazed up at the location of Mars as indicated by the laser, and at 12:45 am applauded Mars for presumably occulting the target star at about the appropriate time. An image of Rob and Beth from somewhat earlier inside the TAO building, and an outside view just before event time, with the laser indicating the position of Mars, follow.

12:15 am, 6 May 2025, Beth and Rob inside the TAO building, waiting for the Mars occultation event (midpoint) of 12:45 am.

12:33 am, Tue 6 May 2025, using a laser to encourage Mars in its effort to occult the target star TYC 1398-00275-1 in the constellation Cancer, while waiting for the occultation midpoint time of 12:45 am Eastern, accompanied by a suitably dramatic moonlit overcast.

Mars or Bust!

(cont.)

Event Night, Mon 05 – Tue 06 May 2025:

TAO, our final salute to the overcast Mars occultation, 12:33 am, Tue 6 May 2025.

The end ... or is it only the beginning?

Shop Talk

Shop Talk

- Ted and Rob

An image of our interior work on remote computer communication at TAO on 4 May 2025 is shown below. We tested multiple AD (AnyDesk) connection routes, including nested paths; as an example I connected by AD to a PC in Clinton, and from there back to TAO, where I linked to a camera I had attached to one of the TAO CPUs; this gave me a nice view of the whiteboard at the front of the TAO building, by a return pathway of about 95 km, through an intermediate CPU. There was no significant delay in this image, despite the complicated route the connections followed. We also implemented AD security protocols so connections could only be made from approved external computers. This was all very satisfying, and entertaining, and will be essential for future remote telescope operations.

A view of the whiteboard seen by a TAO computer with an attached webcam at the front of the room. That image is being forwarded to my computer (bottom left) and its secondary terminal (bottom right), using an AD connection through the local TAO internet. Image 10:30 pm Eastern, Sun 4 May 2025. Running this same image shortly afterwards as a nested AD transfer through an intermediate remote computer in Clinton and back to another at TAO, thus twice *ca.* 47 km distant, also proved feasible.

External Event

We would like to invite you and your club members to attend the upcoming annual four-day Green Bank Star Quest 20, being held June 25 through June 28, 2025. It is the largest star party in the nation that combines both optical and radio astronomy. Held at the Green Bank Observatory, located in Green Bank, West Virginia, the rural location provides the dark skies so envied by many other astronomers.

Green Bank Observatory graciously allows us to hold this star party at their facility, where the infrastructure allows events and lectures to continue, even if there is inclement weather. Large campsites are available in the observing field with nearby hot showers. Bunkhouses are also available for a small fee of \$15 per night to help accommodate astronomers. Anyone paying for the full event for four days may choose to arrive on Tuesday. The camping field and bunkhouse will be available, but the bunkhouse is \$15 for each night you stay, including Tuesday night, if you choose to arrive early.

Each year we choose to have the highest quality speakers available, covering a wide variety of topics that would interest both optical and radio astronomers. Additional information is available at this link: <https://greenbankstarquest.org> .

There will be a 10% group discount for groups of ten or more (**pre-paid and non-refundable, unless the event would get cancelled again due to circumstances out of our control**). **The discount is off of the registration fee only, and does not include bunkhouse, RV sites, or any other special fees.**

Green Bank Observatory has informed us that only service dogs currently in service are allowed on the Observatory. No other animals, including emotional support dogs, will be allowed at or near the visitor center, or anywhere else on the Green Bank campus. Service dogs must remain with their humans at all times, due to liability issues.

For anyone who is interested in attending, a registration form is available on our website. The option to use PayPal is also available on our website: <https://greenbankstarquest.org> .

Our club can be contacted by mail: Central Appalachian Astronomy Club, P.O. Box 211, Grafton, WV 26354-0211, or via the club's website: <https://caacwv.com/contact.htm> , or you can contact the coordinator of the event, our club's vice president, John Taylor, at (304) 265-5514.

Sincerely,

Central Appalachian Astronomy Club, WV

Green Bank Star Quest 20 (cont.)

REGISTRATION FORM GREEN BANK STAR QUEST 20, June 25 -28, 2025

Registration fee is **Per Person** and includes: Attendance to all events at the Visitor Center (including activities for children) and a campsite. (Children 18 and under admitted free but must be accompanied by at least one registered adult). Free bath house facilities for both genders, commemorative registration tag with lanyard. The observing field camp sites are non-electric sites. Electric for battery charging only, is available at the white barn in the camping area. **NO GENERATORS:** They cause Radio Frequency Interference (RFI) with the Radio Telescopes. Please note that a limited number of registrations are available, and it is necessary for us to restrict registration for this event to a **2-day minimum** registration. Green Bank Star Quest has a **"No refund"** policy after June 10, 2025. GBO or CAAC will not be responsible for accidents or stolen items. **Only ADA certified dogs allowed at Star Quest.**

This Mail-In Event Registration form must be postmarked on or before June 8, 2025:		Amount
4 Days	Reg. rate \$125 Per adult - x _____ (# of adults) = _____	
3 Days	Reg. rate \$100 Per adult - x _____ (# of adults) = _____	
2 Days	Reg. rate \$80 Per adult - x _____ (# of adults) = _____	
		Registration Sub Total = _____

Day Pass* \$ 35 x _____ Per adult) = _____
 *Day Pass is for all events at the Visitor Center only. NO overnight camping or use of shower facilities.

Bunkhouse is an extra \$15 per night per person and there are a limited number of spaces available
 Number of Males _____ x \$15 per night = _____ x _____ (No. of nights) = _____
 Number of Females _____ x \$15 per night = _____ x _____ (No. of nights) = _____

Bunkhouse is separated by gender, and is limited to only 30 males, and 30 females. You must provide your own pillow, and sleeping bag. The Bunkhouse is provided on a first-come first-serve basis. You must specify your needs at the time of registration. The Bunkhouse is \$15.00 per person per night, with a minimum of a 2 nights.

RV SITE "For Special Needs ONLY!" RV Length _____ Fee \$30 = _____

The RV Site is LIMITED TO SPECIAL NEEDS; you must notify us in advance of those needs. The RV site is closer to shower facilities and on a paved lot. Electrical hook ups are also limited and **MAY NOT** be available, **NO GENERATORS:** They cause Radio Frequency Interference (RFI) with the Radio Telescopes

Please make your Check or Money Order payable to Green Bank Star Quest- **Total Amount Enclosed:** = _____

Mail this entire form to: **GREEN BANK STAR QUEST, PO BOX 211, GRAFTON, WV 26354-0211**

(Please Print)

Names of Registrants: _____

Address: _____

City, State, Zip: _____

Phone Number and Email Address: _____

*Number and ages of Children 18 and Under attending with you _____

For more information or assistance call John Taylor 304-265-5514 or Jim King (304) 694-0277

Meal Plan: Homestyle Breakfast, and/or Dinner will be offered by GBO. Tickets can be purchased at the Starlight Café. GBO will post a menu around noon on Wednesday. Lunch and snacks available at the Starlight Café.

Free Optional Activity that is included in your registration: The Green Bank Observatory (GBO) will be offering specialized classes and the use of the 40-foot radio telescope, free to a limited number of Star Quest registrants. **Class size and number of classes are limited!** This activity is provided on a first-come first-serve basis. If you are interested: Please sign up at the registration desk when you arrive. You will receive classroom instruction on the objects to be observed. Then at an appointed time, your group will do observing with the 40-foot radio telescope. GBO will work with teams of ten, some will be during the daytime hours and some will be at night. Each team will actually be able to collect real data that can be analyzed. There is no charge to participants for this program. Revision 082824

If you have comments or specials needs , please let us know:

Astrophotography

The ZWO Seestar S-50 smart telescope has recently gotten a nice software upgrade that allows it to be mounted on a wedge. If you select equatorial mode under the new mount menu item, it guides you through the polar alignment process. This involves letting the Seestar take a few images and do plate solving. It then tells you how far off you are and lets you iterate a few times to improve alignment. This allows longer exposures and eliminates problems with field rotation. The image processing also has added a noise reduction algorithm that does a good job. Below are some images I've recently taken in equatorial mode. As indicated below, I took the Seestar with me on a recent trip to San Francisco and used it from my daughter's backyard. It fits nicely in a suitcase.

M51

M3

26 Apr 2025
Oak Ridge, TN

Appendices

Astronomy

- tb

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

1 ly = 1 ly (Julian) = *exactly* 9 460 730 472 580. 8 km = 63 241. 077 084 ... AU
c = speed of light = *exactly* 299 792 458 m/s = *exactly* ☺ 1 ly/yr.
1 AU = *exactly* 149 597 870. 7 km
1 parsec (pc) = 3. 261 598 ... light years (ly)
1 yr (Julian) = *exactly* 365.25 d = *exactly* 31 557 600 s
1 d = *exactly* 86 400 s

distance to α Cen A = 1.346(2) pc = 4.390(8) ly
distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 8 kpc ~ 25 kly (considerable uncertainty)

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m *exactly*
 H_{α} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 0.5 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{1/5}$ x fainter =	1. 584 893 ... x fainter
+ 1 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{2/5}$ x fainter =	2. 511 886 ... x fainter
+ 2 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{4/5}$ x fainter =	6. 309 ... x fainter
+ 2.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^1 x fainter =	10 x fainter
+ 3 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{6/5}$ x fainter =	15. 848 ... x fainter
+ 4 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{8/5}$ x fainter =	39. 810 ... x fainter
+ 5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^2 x fainter =	100 x fainter
+ 6 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{12/5}$ x fainter =	251. 188 ... x fainter
+ 7.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^3 x fainter =	1000 x fainter
+ 8 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{16/5}$ x fainter =	1584. 893 ... x fainter
+ 10 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^4 x fainter =	10 000 x fainter
+ 20 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^8 x fainter =	100 000 000 x fainter

Brightness is proportional to $1 / \text{distance}^2$

10 x more distant = *exactly* 10^2 x fainter = + 5 change in magnitude
 10^2 x more distant = *exactly* 10^4 x fainter = + 10 change in mag
 10^3 x more distant = *exactly* 10^6 x fainter = + 15 change in mag

Absolute magnitude M_{abs} is the brightness as seen from a distance of 10 pc
 M_{abs} (our sun) = 4.83

17th mag is about 1 optical photon / cm^2 s (Barnes's rule ☺)

Astronomy (cont.)

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate. *Exact* numerical relationships are indicated as such.

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = the angle ϕ around the celestial polar axis, usually quoted in hours, minutes, and seconds (*h m s*); analogous to longitude.

Dec = Declination = the angle θ above the celestial equator, usually quoted in degrees, minutes, and seconds ($^{\circ} \ ' \ ''$); analogous to latitude.

The RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles, together with a reference epoch such as J2000.0, specify an object's direction in the sky.

A unit length vector ("unit vector") $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ pointing towards an object in the sky ("on the celestial sphere") in terms of RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\eta} = \cos(\theta) \cos(\phi) \mathbf{x} + \cos(\theta) \sin(\phi) \mathbf{y} + \sin(\theta) \mathbf{z} = C(c \mathbf{x} + s \mathbf{y}) + S \mathbf{z}$$

The arc angle Θ_{12} between any two directions in the sky $\boldsymbol{\eta}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_2$ (or any two stars) using the dot product formula and some obvious abbreviations, satisfies

$$\cos(\Theta_{12}) = \sin(\theta_1)\sin(\theta_2) + \cos(\theta_1)\cos(\theta_2)\cos(\phi_1 - \phi_2) = S_1 S_2 + C_1 C_2 c_{1-2}$$

$$1 \text{ degree} = \pi/180 \text{ radians} = 1.745 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcmin} = \pi/10800 \text{ radians} = 2.909 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcsec} = 1 \text{ asec} = \pi/648000 \text{ radians} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ mas} = 10^{-3} \text{ asec} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 km} = 4.848 \text{ mm}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 AU} = 725.3 \text{ km}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 pc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$1 \text{ mas @ 1 kpc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

JD = Julian Date (Astronomer's calendar) = a simple count of days starting at noon UT on Monday 1 Jan 4713 BC. That date and time was the start of Julian Day 0. The current JD can be inferred from the value on the cover of the Trapezium.

The 80 Brightest Stars

The 80 brightest stars (c/o Wikipedia), and their distances from Earth in light years, the first 40 with errors (from Gaia data).

1	Sirius	8.709	0.005	41	Menkalinan	81.1
2	Canopus	309.	16.	42	Atria	390.6
3	alpha Centauri A	4.395	0.008	43	Alhena	109.3
4	Arcturus	36.7	0.2	44	Peacock	178.8
5	Vega	25.04	0.07	45	Alsephina	80.6
6	Capella	42.81	0.26	46	Mirzam	492.7
7	Rigel	863.	78.	47	Polaris	432.6
8	Procyon	11.46	0.05	48	Alphard	177.3
9	Archenar	139.4	3.4	49	Hamal	65.8
10	Betelgeuse	498.	63.	50	Diphda	96.3
11	beta Centauri	392.	24.	51	Mizar	97.8
12	Altair	16.73	0.05	52	Nunki	227.8
13	alpha Crucis	322.	16.	53	Menkent	58.8
14	Aldebaran	66.64	1.05	54	Alpheratz	97.0
15	Antares	554.	94.	55	Mirach	197.4
16	Spica	250.	13.	56	Rasalhague	48.6
17	Pollux	33.78	0.09	57	Algieba	130.1
18	Fomalhaut	25.13	0.09	58	Kochab	130.9
19	Deneb	1410	200	59	Saiph	647.1
20	Mimosa	279.	23.	60	Denebola	35.9
21	Regulus	79.30	0.67	61	Algol	94.0
22	Adhara	405.	7.0	62	Tiaki	177.0
23	Castor	50.68	0.032	63	Muhlifain	130.2
24	Shaula	571.2	7.5	64	Aspidiske	765.6
25	Gacrux	88.56	0.43	65	Suhail	544.5
26	Bellatrix	252.4	10.2	66	Alphecca	75.0
27	Elnath	133.9	1.9	67	Mintaka	692.5
28	Miaplacidus	113.2	0.43	68	Sadr	1832.3
29	Alnilam	1980	540	69	Eltanin	154.3
30	Regor	1120	110	70	Schedar	228.2
31	Alnair	101.0	0.66	71	Naos	1083.6
32	Alnitak	736.	106.	72	Almach	393.0
33	Alioth	82.55	0.42	73	Caph	54.7
34	Dubhe	122.9	2.2	74	Izar	235.8
35	Mirfak	506.	13.	75	alpha Lupi	464.6
36	Wezen	1610	300	76	epsilon Centauri	427.5
37	Sargas	300.	41.	77	Dschubba	491.2
38	Kaus Australis	143.3	1.5	78	Larawag	63.7
39	Avior	605.	47.	79	eta Centauri	305.7
40	Alkaid	103.9	0.79	80	Merak	79.7

Notable Star-Pair Angles

Notable star pairs (from the set of the 80 brightest stars listed above) that are close to a multiple of 5° separation. The angles are in degrees.

		<u>Θ</u>	<u>Δθ</u>	<u>defect (%)</u>
Schedar	Caph	5	-0.085	1.7
Betelgeuse	Alnitak	10	0.017	0.17
Capella	Castor	30	-0.023	0.077
Procyon	Mirzam	30	-0.094	0.31
Elnath	Alnilam	30	-0.096	0.32
Alpheratz	Caph	30	0.060	0.20
Aldebaran	Pollux	45	0.013	0.029
Betelgeuse	Algol	50	-0.033	0.066
Alnitak	Naos	50	-0.049	0.098
Pollux	Alioth	60	0.065	0.11
Gacrux	Alphard	60	-0.001	0.002
Regulus	Bellatrix	70	-0.030	0.043
Sirius	Mirfak	80	-0.094	0.12
alpha_Centauri	Regulus	90	0.057	0.063
Vega	Denebola	90	-0.065	0.072
Fomalhaut	Caph	90	0.006	0.007
Deneb	Alnilam	120	0.059	0.049
Menkent	Mintaka	120	0.000	0.000
Sirius	Alphecca	135	-0.089	0.066
Aldebaran	Antares	170	-0.021	0.012

Exeunt

The War of the Worlds

No one would have believed in the last years of the nineteenth century that this world was being watched keenly and closely by intelligences greater than man's and yet as mortal as his own; that as men busied themselves about their various concerns they were scrutinised and studied, perhaps almost as narrowly as a man with a microscope might scrutinise the transient creatures that swarm and multiply in a drop of water. With infinite complacency men went to and fro over this globe about their little affairs, serene in their assurance of their empire over matter. It is possible that the infusoria under the microscope do the same. No one gave a thought to the older worlds of space as sources of human danger, or thought of them only to dismiss the idea of life upon them as impossible or improbable. It is curious to recall some of the mental habits of those departed days. At most terrestrial men fancied there might be other men upon Mars, perhaps inferior to themselves and ready to welcome a missionary enterprise. Yet across the gulf of space, minds that are to our minds as ours are to those of the beasts that perish, intellects vast and cool and unsympathetic, regarded this earth with envious eyes, and slowly and surely drew their plans against us.

- H. G. Wells
(1895-1897)
publ. 1898

ORION and TAO (and Obed) General Information (links)

May be found at the following URLs:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tamke-Allan_Observatory

<http://www.orioninc.org/>

<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

<https://www.facebook.com/ORIONAstronomyTN/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/454645124557215>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tamke-Allan%20Observatory/120477734665841>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/index.htm>

<https://twitter.com/TAOremote>

ORIONastronomy@groups.io

Where is TAO?

334 Caney Creek Rd, Rockwood, TN 37854

N 35° 49' 57", W 84° 37' 04"; Alt. 324 m

Where is Obed?

Lilly Bluff Overlook

N 36° 06' 09", W 84° 43' 17"; Alt. 402 m

Nemo Bridge (on the bridge, E bank of Emory River)

N 36° 04' 07", W 84° 39' 43"; Alt. 268 m

Trapezium back issues online:

Vol. 49, Issue 4; Fri 15 Apr 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219253
Vol. 49, Issue 5; Fri 12 May 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8216818
Vol. 49, Issue 6; Fri 16 Jun 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8030659
Vol. 49, Issue 7; Fri 14 Jul 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8140396
Vol. 49, Issue 8; Fri 18 Aug 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8251302
Vol. 49, Issue 9; Fri 15 Sep 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8336647
Vol. 49, Issue 10; Fri 13 Oct 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8433081
Vol. 49, Issue 11; Fri 17 Nov 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10138151
Vol. 49, Issue 12; Fri 15 Dec 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10382618
Vol. 50, Issue 01; Fri 12 Jan 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10483283
Vol. 50, Issue 02; Fri 16 Feb 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10672625
Vol. 50, Issue 03; Fri 15 Mar 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10822600
Vol. 50, Issue 04; Fri 12 Apr 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10967036
Vol. 50, Issue 05; Fri 10 May 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11176951
Vol. 50, Issue 06; Fri 14 Jun 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11646971
Vol. 50, Issue 07, Fri 12 Jul 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735071
Vol. 50, Issue 08, Fri 16 Aug 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13333599
Vol. 50, Issue 09, Fri 13 Sep 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13742825
Vol. 50, Issue 10, Fri 11 Oct 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13921735
Vol. 50, Issue 11, Fri 15 Nov 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14171218
Vol. 50, Issue 12, Fri 13 Dec 2024:	https://zenodo.org/records/14394899
Vol. 51, Issue 01, Fri 10 Jan 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/14630165
Vol. 51, Issue 02, Fri 14 Feb 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/14873015
Vol. 51, Issue 03, Fri 14 Mar 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/15015954
Vol. 51, Issue 04, Fri 11 Apr 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/15200349
Vol. 51, Issue 05, Fri 16 May 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/15443035

A generic link that lists Trapezium pdf issues (and other ORION documents) starting with the most recent, which does not require a specific zenodo document number, follows:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/rigel/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Fin du journal

Nebula Felinica